

SINAI Team at ToxHabits: Toxic Habit Extraction with EuroBERT and Instruction-Tuned Language Models

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Abstract

The extraction of information about toxic habits such as tobacco, alcohol, cannabis, and recreational drug use from clinical narratives is crucial for enhancing patient care and supporting epidemiological studies. The ToxHabits shared task addresses this challenge by providing a Spanish corpus annotated with event-based structures to capture substances and their clinical modifiers. This paper presents the SINAI team’s participation in ToxHabits, proposing a hybrid approach that combines a domain-adapted transformer encoder (EuroBERT) for named entity recognition (ToxNER) with an instruction-tuned large language model for contextual attribute extraction (ToxUSE). Our system integrates dynamic retrieval of similar examples and generative prompting to tackle the complexities of Spanish clinical text. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of combining domain-specific transformers with generative strategies for the comprehensive extraction of substance use information.

Keywords

Biomedical NLP; Toxic habits; Named Entity Recognition; Event extraction; Spanish clinical text; EuroBERT; Large Language Models; Generative prompting

1. Introducción

The presence of toxic habits such as tobacco, alcohol, cannabis, and recreational drug use has a substantial impact on patient health outcomes, making their detection in clinical narratives a priority for biomedical Natural Language Processing (NLP). Automatic extraction of this information from electronic health records (EHRs) is essential to support secondary applications such as epidemiological studies, clinical decision support systems, and risk factor monitoring. However, this information is often embedded in unstructured text, requiring specialized techniques for its effective extraction and representation.

The ToxHabits shared task focuses on the extraction of substance-related information from Spanish clinical documents. This task introduces a novel corpus annotated with event-based structures that reflect not only the substances mentioned but also their associated clinical modifiers (e.g., frequency, method, history). The competition is structured into two subtasks: *ToxNER*, which targets the recognition and classification of toxic substance mentions, and *ToxUSE*, which aims to extract contextual modifiers linked to each mention [1]. In this paper, we present the SINAI team’s approach, which combines transformer-based models (EuroBERT) [2] with generative prompting strategies using large language models (LLMs) to address the challenges of both subtasks effectively.

2. Related Work

The extraction of substance use information from clinical narratives has gained importance due to its impact on public health surveillance and patient care. Early approaches were mainly rule-based or dictionary-driven [3], but showed limited generalization.

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With the rise of transformer-based models, performance in biomedical named entity recognition (NER) has significantly improved [4][5]. For Spanish medical texts, domain-adapted models such as Spanish-BERT or mBERT have shown promising results, despite the scarcity of annotated data. Recent contributions by the SINAI group have advanced NER and concept normalization for Spanish clinical narratives in various shared tasks [6][7][8][9], highlighting the benefit of domain-specific encoders combined with hybrid normalization pipelines.

Beyond entity recognition, event-based frameworks extract richer contextual information by linking mentions with attributes like frequency, amount, and method. Resources such as SHAC [10] and n2c2 datasets [11] have supported this in English, but remain scarce for Spanish. Recently, large language models (LLMs) with generative prompting and few-shot learning have shown promise for relation extraction and event structuring [12].

Building on these advances, our system combines a transformer encoder for NER with a generative LLM module for contextual attribute extraction, using dynamic retrieval and adaptive prompts to tackle the challenges posed by limited resources and complex event structures in the ToxHabits shared task.

3. Methodology

3.1. Corpus description and tasks

The ToxHabits competition uses a corpus of 1,500 clinical texts in Spanish, anonymized and sourced from real medical records and open biomedical literature, focused on the study of toxic habits. This corpus is manually annotated following an event schema that identifies substances and their modifiers in a clinical context, adapted from the SHAC corpus for the Spanish domain used in the 2022 n2c2/UW shared task. The annotations, carried out with the *brat* tool [13], capture hierarchical relations, overlapping events, and multiple arguments.

Main entities. The substances under study are grouped into four classes:

- Tobacco: Products related to tobacco or smoking habits.
- Alcohol: Mentions of alcoholic beverage consumption.
- Cannabis: References to cannabis, marijuana, or derivatives.
- Drug: Unspecified substances, recreational drugs, or other potentially abusive medications.

Clinical modifiers. Each substance mention can be associated with the following attributes:

- Type: Specific type or form of the substance (e.g., “red wine”).
- Method: Route of administration (e.g., “smoked”, “oral”).
- Amount: Amount consumed (e.g., “1–2 g/day”).
- Frequency: Frequency of consumption (e.g., “daily”).
- Duration: Duration of the habit (e.g., “since age 16”).
- History: Information about the consumption history (e.g., “former smoker”).

Figure 1: Example of an annotation from the ToxHabits corpus. Translation: *(The patient) reported having inhaled heroin eight days earlier.*

Figure 2: Example of a document annotated in *brat*. Translation: *51-year-old male with a history of polysubstance use. Currently consumes 1–2 g/day of cannabis orally.*

Competition subtasks. The competition is structured into two complementary subtasks:

- **ToxNER: Substance mention identification.** This subtask consists of recognizing and classifying entities corresponding to the four substance classes described above. It focuses on identifying explicit mentions in the clinical text, serving as a basis for a structured representation of consumption.
- **ToxUSE: Clinical modifier detection.** Based on the entities detected in ToxNER, this subtask aims to extract the contextual modifiers mentioned. It requires establishing a semantic relation between each modifier and its corresponding entity, generating a rich and precise representation of the consumption pattern.

3.2. Approach to ToxNER

For the named entity recognition subtask, the EuroBERT family of models is used, specialized in European languages, including Spanish. Its main advantage is the ability to process long sequences of up to 8192 tokens, compared to the usual 512 tokens in standard *encoders*, which facilitates handling extensive texts. To achieve proper labeling by the model, a mapping strategy is developed that includes:

1. **Text segmentation:** The text is split into words using whitespace separation. Punctuation marks adjacent to words are separated.
2. **Positional mapping:** Each word is located at its exact position in the original text using character offsets.
3. **Label creation:** Character-level labels are generated using BIO scheme based on the JSON annotations.
4. **Token-label assignment:** EuroBERT’s internal tokenizer handles the mapping from character-level labels to subword tokens, with multi-token mentions managed through the standard BIO mechanism where the first subtoken receives the B- tag and subsequent subtokens receive I- tags.

Labeling scheme: A standard BIO tagging scheme is adopted to handle entity boundaries properly. The set of labels includes:

$$\mathcal{L} = \{0, \text{B-Tobacco}, \text{I-Tobacco}, \text{B-Alcohol}, \text{I-Alcohol}, \text{B-Cannabis}, \text{I-Cannabis}, \text{B-Drug}, \text{I-Drug}\}$$

where 0 represents tokens that do not belong to any entity, B- prefixes mark the beginning of entity spans, and I- prefixes mark the continuation of multi-token entities.

3.3. Approach to ToxUSE

For the clinical modifiers extraction subtask, a hybrid strategy is developed that combines transformer-based entity recognition with generative natural language processing and similar example retrieval

techniques. This approach treats ToxUSE as a context-conditioned generation task, using ToxNER predictions as a starting point to identify associated clinical modifiers.

System architecture: The methodology is structured into three main components:

1. **Base entity extraction:** ToxNER predictions are used as input, extracting toxic substance entities along with the full sentence containing each entity as contextual information.
2. **Similarity-based retrieval system:** For each entity identified in the test set, a textual corpus is built from all annotated entities in the training set. TF-IDF vectorization is employed for computational efficiency, calculating cosine similarity between vector representations:

$$\text{sim}(e_{\text{test}}, e_{\text{train}}) = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{\text{test}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{\text{train}}}{\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{test}}\| \cdot \|\mathbf{v}_{\text{train}}\|}$$

where \mathbf{v}_{test} and $\mathbf{v}_{\text{train}}$ represent the TF-IDF representations of the test and training entities, respectively. TF-IDF was chosen over semantic embeddings (e.g., SBERT) due to computational efficiency and the specific nature of clinical entity matching, where lexical overlap often indicates relevant similarity.

3. **Generation via LLM:** Models from the OpenAI family are employed to extract specific clinical modifiers using *few-shot prompting*. The generation system operates by building adaptive prompts that include: (i) base instructions for modifier extraction, (ii) the k most similar examples retrieved in the previous step in input-output format, and (iii) the target entity for processing. The exact prompt template used is provided in Appendix A.

4. Results

4.1. Experimental setup

The experiments were conducted using a validation set of the *ToxHabits* corpus, composed of 300 clinical documents (20% of the total), randomly selected from the training set.

Subtask 1 – ToxNER. For substance mention detection, models based on the EuroBERT architecture were trained. Two configurations with different parameter counts were evaluated:

- **EuroBERT-210:** Model with 210 million parameters.
- **EuroBERT-610:** Model with 610 million parameters.

Both models used a context window of 4096 tokens instead of their full 8192 capacity due to GPU memory limitations during training.

The following hyperparameters were used:

- **Learning rate:** 2×10^{-5}
- **Weight decay:** 0.01
- **Batch size:** 2 (limited by GPU memory)
- **Epochs:** 15
- **Optimizer:** AdamW

Subtask 2 – ToxUSE. For the extraction of consumption modifiers, generative language models from the OpenAI family (GPT-4o-mini, GPT-4.1-mini, and GPT-4.1) were employed.

Five different configurations were explored, evaluating the impact of example type and number using a base *prompt*.

4.2. Results Analysis

Evaluation metrics. All reported metrics are macro averages computed at the entity level using BIO tagging scheme. Entity-level evaluation requires exact span matching: an entity is considered correct only when both the begin and end character offsets of the predicted span match exactly with the gold standard annotations.

Subtask 1 – ToxNER. The results obtained with the EuroBERT models on the named entity recognition task are as follows:

Model	Precision	Recall	F1
EuroBERT-210	0.7620	0.8083	0.7919
EuroBERT-610	0.7020	0.7406	0.7204

Table 1

ToxNER results on the validation set.

The EuroBERT-210 model achieved the best overall performance, surpassing its larger version by more than 7 F1 points. This result suggests that, in this scenario, a more compact model may better adapt to the specific clinical domain of the corpus. A possible explanation is that, although both models were trained for the same number of epochs, the larger model (EuroBERT-610) requires a longer fine-tuning process to reach its full potential due to its greater capacity and complexity.

Subtask 2 – ToxUSE. In this subtask, the use of dynamic examples significantly improved the system’s performance. The results of the different evaluated configurations are shown below:

Configuration	Model	Static Ex.	Dynamic Ex.	Precision	Recall	F1
1	GPT-4o-mini	2	0	0.3531	0.2157	0.2678
2	GPT-4o-mini	2	1	0.5848	0.5045	0.5417
3	GPT-4o-mini	0	3	0.6440	0.6268	0.6353
4	GPT-4.1-mini	0	3	0.6242	0.6829	0.6522
5	GPT-4.1-mini (end-to-end)	0	3	0.5651	0.6236	0.5929

Table 2

ToxUSE results on the validation set with different example combinations.

Approaches 1 to 4 were evaluated using the actual entities from the validation set, i.e., assuming that the substance mentions were known in advance. In this context, the best result was obtained with Approach 4, which combines the GPT-4.1-mini model with three automatically selected dynamic examples. However, Approach 5 represents a more realistic scenario: it starts from the entities predicted by the EuroBERT model (ToxNER) and is evaluated against the reference entities. This discrepancy between prediction and reference introduces accumulated errors that negatively impact overall performance, reflected in a decrease in F1.

Final evaluation on the test set. After the validation phase, the best-performing approaches were selected for application on the official *ToxHabits* challenge test set. Specifically, the **EuroBERT-210** model was used for the ToxNER subtask, and for the ToxUSE subtask, the **GPT-4.1** model with dynamic examples was employed.

Although only the GPT-4 *mini* versions could be used during validation due to resource limitations, the superiority of GPT-4.1-mini in this phase led to the inference that the full GPT-4.1 version would deliver even better performance on the final test set.

These results reflect the effectiveness of the developed systems, with particularly high performance in substance mention detection (ToxNER), thanks to the EuroBERT-210 model. Likewise, the use of

Subtask	Precision	Recall	F1
ToxNER (EuroBERT-210)	0.89	0.89	0.89
ToxUSE (GPT-4.1)	0.78	0.79	0.78

Table 3

Results obtained on the official test set.

prompting with dynamic examples and the GPT-4.1 model enabled reaching a competitive F1 score in the clinical modifier extraction subtask (ToxUSE).

However, it is important to highlight that the official results on the test set differ significantly from those obtained during the internal validation phase. This discrepancy may be attributed to several factors: (i) the distribution and characteristics of the test dataset being substantially different from those of the validation set used, and (ii) the use of the full GPT-4.1 model instead of GPT-4.1-mini during final evaluation, which may exhibit different behavior patterns. These factors combined suggest a greater challenge for the systems and reflect the complexity of the problem in a more realistic scenario, where model scaling and dataset shift can significantly impact performance.

4.3. Error Analysis

Errors in ToxNER. Most errors were concentrated in two areas:

- **Implicit entities:** indirect mentions or infrequent synonyms were not detected.
- **Mentions not annotated as events:** the model correctly identified certain substances as entities, but these were not considered events by the annotators, leading to false positives during evaluation.

Errors in ToxUSE. The main challenges detected in modifier extraction were:

- **Temporal misalignment:** difficulty in correctly associating expressions such as “currently” or “for the past 10 years” with the corresponding entity.
- **Modifier confusion:** errors in classifying terms like “occasionally” between History and Frequency.

5. Conclusions

This work presents the participation of the SINAI team in the ToxHabits challenge, focused on the extraction of toxic habits from clinical texts in Spanish. Two complementary approaches were proposed: one based on EuroBERT for substance recognition (ToxNER), and a hybrid method combining example retrieval and generative models for the extraction of clinical modifiers (ToxUSE). The results show that more compact models can provide competitive performance in specific domains, and that the incorporation of dynamic examples significantly improves generation quality in complex tasks.

These findings reinforce the value of adaptive and contextualized approaches in clinical NLP, where data scarcity and textual variability pose significant challenges. Furthermore, it is evident that combining discriminative and generative models, together with retrieval techniques, is an effective strategy for complex semantic extraction tasks in specialized texts.

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Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the authors used generative AI in order to: Grammar and spelling check. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the publication's content.

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A. Prompt Template

The exact prompt template used for ToxUSE modifier extraction:

Eres un modelo de extracción de argumentos en un corpus de hábitos tóxicos. Tu entrada siempre tendrá tres campos:

```
{
  ``trigger_type``: ``<Tipo de trigger: Tobacco|Cannabis|Alcohol|Drug>``,
  ``trigger_text``: ``<Texto tal cual del trigger>``,
  ``text``: ``<Texto completo en el que extraer argumentos>``
}
```

Tu tarea es devolver un único objeto JSON con todos los argumentos detectados *alrededor* de ese trigger. Debes extraer las siguientes seis clases de argumentos tal cual como aparece en el texto original, sin ninguna modificación:

- **Type:** ¿qué tipo de sustancia?
- **Method:** forma de administración (intravenoso, inhalado...).
- **Amount:** cantidad (e.g. “2 copas”, “10 cigarrillos”).
- **Frequency:** periodicidad (“cada día”, “una vez al año”).
- **Duration:** duración (“durante dos años”, “desde enero”).
- **History:** momento de cese (“en 2007”, “hace tres meses”).
- **StatusTime:** indica si es consumo *actual* o *pasado*. Emplea el campo adicional ```StatusTimeVal``: ``current``|``past```, en caso de que no se indique será None o en caso de que no sea consumidor ni lo haya sido.

Solo debes de extraer aquellos que estén presentes, excepto StatusTime que siempre es obligatorio.

Instrucciones de formato

1. El diccionario que debes de devolver incluye un array (u objeto con claves “T1”, “T2”, ...) llamado ```arguments```.
2. Para cada argumento, devuelve:
 - ```argument_type```
 - ```argument_text```
 - ```argument_start_span```
 - ```argument_end_span```
3. Si no aparece algún tipo, sencillamente no lo incluyas en el JSON.